

Definition of Case Study Teams for the ERGA stream within the BGE project

Version 1

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The aims of the Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE) - European Reference Genome Atlas (ERGA) stream (in the following referred to as BGE-ERGA) are to establish and implement large-scale biodiversity genomic data generation pipelines for Europe to accelerate the production and accessibility of reference-quality, complete genome sequences for species across the whole of European biodiversity for biodiversity characterisation, conservation and biomonitoring. The BGE-ERGA stream focuses on reference-quality genomes from critical European biodiversity, biodiversity hotspots, pollinators, and BGE-ERGA applied case studies.

This **Definition of Case Study Teams** is an extension of the [Genome Team](#) definition and pertains only to case studies developed in the BGE-ERGA stream.

The Case Studies within BGE-ERGA will develop genomic applications anchored in Reference Genomes and imply the collection of population sampling and additional genome data. The generation of the reference genomes is performed by a Genome Team and is not the object of this document. The work associated with a Case Study leading to the development of a genome application within BGE-ERGA is performed by a **Case Study Team**. Each Case Study Team includes a set of roles, delivered by individuals or collectives, and it is agreed that delivery to these roles is sufficient engagement to warrant authorship on the emerging Case Study publication. Single individuals may take on several roles from the list below, and some roles may be delivered by collectives.

Case Study Team Member Roles

- 1) Case Study Coordinator (also coordinating the Case Study Team)
- 2) Researchers and experts delivering support for case study management
- 3) Sample collector(s) and/or sample provider(s)
- 4) Taxonomic expert(s) making or affirming diagnosis of samples to species
- 5) Collections curator(s) delivering vouchering and/or biobanking of the samples
- 6) Researchers and experts delivering support for sample management and sample handling
- 7) Researchers and technical experts delivering primary laboratory processing of samples, including nucleic acid extraction and quality assessment (including maintenance and management of facilities)
- 8) Researchers and technical experts delivering library preparation and sequencing, except if done via outsourcing.
- 9) Researchers and technical experts delivering sequence data processing including data quality control and curation.
- 10) Researchers and technical experts delivering data analysis and manuscript writing.
- 11) Researchers and technical experts involved in stakeholder engagement and delivering stakeholder-related activities.
- 12) Researchers and technical experts delivering mentorship for any case study-related activity.

The Case Study Coordinator role

The Case Study Coordinator has specific roles to ensure coordination and co-working across the Case Study Team. In particular, the Case Study Coordinator will be responsible to communicate updates on the progress of the case study development to the Task and Work Package Leaders, ensure that all procedures comply with the policies of the BGE project, and guarantee that contributors to the

Case Study development are properly acknowledged and included in the Case Study Team. The Case Study Coordinator will organise and delegate as required to acquire and ship samples, including obtaining legal permits, DNA barcoding, metadata recording, sample manifest completion, safe storage of samples, vouchering and biobanking, if applicable. The Case Study Coordinator will organise and delegate as required data collection and analyses and the engagement of stakeholders. By agreeing to this document, the Case Study Coordinator and all members of the corresponding Case Study Team agree that all samples included in the case study can be used for sequencing and that resulting data can be released Open Access following the FAIR and CARE data principles as required per EU regulations.

Nature of the collaboration

All Case Study Team members are collaborators and co-authors in the corresponding Genome Application publication and agree with the Open Access Data Sharing policy adopted by BGE for Case Study development [add link, tbd], which adheres to FAIR and CARE principles as requested by the European Union. Members can be added during the development of the case study. Involved local community partners will be acknowledged or included as co-authors.

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